

Effects of Ethno-mathematics Approach on Achievement in Number and Numeration concept among Junior Secondary School Students in Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study was designed to determine the effects of ethnomathematics approach on achievement in number and numeration concept among junior secondary school students in Akwa Ibom State. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest posttest non-equivalent control group was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all government coeducational Junior Secondary School class one (JSSI) students of 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State. 440 (214 Male and 226 Female) JSSI students constitutes the sample size from the target population. The sample size was arrived at by selecting eleven government coeducational secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State using simple random sampling technique. The sample schools were explored using an intact class. Mathematics Achievement Test on Number and Numeration (MATNN) was used as instrument for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The reliability of the instruments was established using Kuder Richardson KR-21 with a reliability coefficient of 0.75. Mean, Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions and Independent t-test statistics to test null hypotheses at $P < .05$. The results revealed among others that ethnomathematics approach was more effective in facilitating students' achievement in number and numeration. The study therefore concluded that using ethnomathematics approach in teaching and learning of mathematics concept would enhance students' educational gains. The researcher recommended that ethnomathematics approach should be adopted in our school to capture the attention of the students in learning mathematics.

Keyword: Ethnomathematics approach, Academic achievement, Number and Numeration.

Introduction

Mathematics is the life of all scientific and technological activities of man. Mathematics helps children find meaning in their environment. As they learn to reason, connect ideas, and think logically, they gain important tools and concepts for making sense out of the world, and thus construct a solid foundation for success in school. Hence, mathematical ability is crucial for the economic success of societies. It is also important in the scientific and technological development of countries (Enu, Agyman, & Nkum, 2015). This is because mathematics skills are essential in understanding other disciplines including engineering, sciences, social sciences and even the arts (Phonapichat, Wongwanich, & Sujiva, 2014). Abe and Gbenro (2014) point out that mathematics plays a multidimensional role in science and technology of which its application outspread to all areas of science, technology as well as business enterprises. Due to the importance that mathematics engulfs, the subject became key in school curriculum. According to Ngussa and Mbuti (2017), the mathematics curriculum is intended to provide students with knowledge and skills that are essential in the changing technological world.

Ekwueme (2018) defines Mathematics as a creation of human mind, which basically is concerned with ideas, processes and reasoning. Ekwueme (2018) also described it as the study of measurements, relationships and properties of quantities and sets; hence, its list of definitions is in exhaustive. Stressing the role of Mathematics in various vocations, Ekwueme (2018) made it clear that there is virtually no profession in today's world one can specialize in without doing Mathematics, thus one deceives himself who thinks of any profession without Mathematics especially when it comes to the art of creation and imagination. Hence, people of all trades and professions apply some level of the knowledge of mathematics in everyday of their lives. For instance, the trader in the market, the driver on the steering, the clergy on the pulpit, the cook in the kitchen, the fisherman on his oars, the nurse in the hospital ward, everybody, has an iota of something to do with mathematics.

Mathematics equips the learner to reason logically and know-how to reach a reasonable conclusion from a given premise (Azuka and Okwuoza, 2015). The indispensability and usefulness of mathematics in nation building and everyday living cannot be overstressed.

Thus, owing to its wide range of applicability, most countries of the world including Nigeria, realized this fact, and made mathematics compulsory in primary and secondary schools. Presently, majority of universities and other tertiary institutions in Nigeria demand a credit pass in mathematics before admission. Unfortunately, students’ achievements in this subject in public examinations for many years now have remained poor. The worrisome poor states of mathematics education in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State are glaring to all. The poor teaching and learning of Mathematics concepts has in turn led to massive failure of students in Mathematics, in both internal and external examinations and shown in the table below is the students’ results in the senior secondary school examination in Akwa Ibom State organized by WAEC.

Table1: Percentage of students in Akwa Ibom State that obtained credit and above (A1- C6) pass and below (D7- F9) in the May/June WASSCE in general mathematics between 2016 and 2021

Year	% with credit and above including Mathematics and English Language	% with pass and below
2016	49.8%	51.2%
2017	60.9%	39.1%
2018	53.9%	46.1%
2019	48.7%	51.3%
2020	60.5%	39.5%
2021	84.1%	15.9%

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, 2022

According to Abasi (2018b), the deplorable state of mathematics achievement is attributed to a number of factors ranging from teachers competency on the subject matter, learners’ attitude and perception, instructional strategies and materials as well as availability and utilization of mathematics laboratory kits. For a successful mathematics instruction to take place, it is pertinent that every mathematics teacher should engage the students actively with concrete materials to aid the teaching and learning process (Abasi, 2018a). This may help to build confidence in the mind of those who before now have formed within themselves that “mathematics is not for them”. This is because methods used in teaching mathematics are foreign, euro-centric in nature and firmly rooted in alien culture. Mathematics is taught in foreign language. This has degenerated to lack of understanding of mathematical problems presented to the students. They neither understood its basic principles, computations, logic nor the mathematical concept formation; consequently they resort to learning by rote memorization which is not a guarantee for success in learning retention and mastering. In this respect, teachers have been advised to use teaching methods or approaches that would enhance students’ interest in the learning of mathematics thereby resulting into better performance (Ado & Abasi, 2014).

Due to peculiarities, researchers in mathematics education Edoho and Abasi (2019); Ado and Abasi (2021a); Abasi and Ado (2021) and other prominent stakeholders, like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) have in recent times been beaming their search light on conceptual means and method that could promote the level of teaching and learning mathematics. However, none of these research efforts have shown significant positive influence on students’ mathematics achievement. According to Abasi (2024), an instructional situation whereby the student is featured as the active participant while the teacher assumes the roles of a facilitator, mediator and assessor of learning have been found to be superior in developing students’ abilities in applying concepts to personal growth, developing positive attitudes, fostering motivation, and encouraging appropriate cognitive skills. It is on this premise that the researchers try to seek solution to this persistent poor achievement of students in mathematics using cultural and home based activity approach.

Mathematics exists in the child's cultural environment and it could be used in school to change the perception of mathematics as foreign and abstract. It is this mathematics as perceived across cultures that has crystallized into a field of study known as "Ethnomathematics". Kurumeh (2006) used ethnomathematics approach to investigate performance of students. However, her investigation was centered on geometry and mensuration. She found that Ethnomathematics approach made significant difference in the achievement of experimental and control groups. Could this be true of number and numeration in Akwa Ibom State Junior secondary school students?

Ethnomathematics is a link between mathematics and culture. In other words, it brings mathematics and culture together forming a connection between the surroundings of the child and the world of mathematics. Ethnomathematics approach is a creative, cultural, home and activity based approach to the teaching and learning of mathematics. Ethnomathematics is mathematics as part of one's culture. It is the cultural utility of mathematics as science. It centers on using mathematics as it is observed in one's culture and tradition of the people (D'Ambrosio 2018). Ethnomathematics centers on the learner's previous experiences, his/her immediate environment and background in order to build the future. It focuses on what learners' already know and/or background, immediate environment, interests, abilities, talents and cultural activities. Ethnomathematics approach connects the past to the present in order to build the future. This makes mathematics functional and relevant to the needs of the learners and public at large. Ethnomathematics instructions develop students' mathematical abilities, increased creativity and a sound set of research habits, as they learn the required mathematics. This approach suffices to help in overcoming the problem of rote memorization of mathematical concepts, processes, principles, logic and computations by the students. The approach gives students the opportunity to learn by doing, to be actively involved and to some extent that the learner is the principal person in the instructional process.

According to Erukoha (2010), mathematics, whether in the traditional or modern societies is a way of thinking and the best way to teach mathematics is to introduce it in such a way that it will not be at variance with the child's thinking pattern. This is the essence of teaching from ethnomathematics to school mathematics. According to him, children love learning but they do not love paying attention. To get them pay attention, the teacher must engage them with what interests them. Mathematics can become interesting to children if it is presented to them using ethnomathematics pedagogy. Ethnomathematics pedagogy will help to create awareness among children that mathematics is not a euro-centric subject designed to drill them and instill meaningless algorithms into them. It will help them to see mathematics as ubiquitous in their homes, in the games they play and this perception will help them see how home mathematics translates into school mathematics Erukoha, (2010).

Since ethnomathematics is considered as a systematic, captivating and consistent tool or way of giving mathematics instruction in schools, it is therefore pertinent to consider those variables under which if properly incorporated with the ethnomathematics concepts will foster the teaching and learning of mathematics. When talking about ethnomathematics, one should consider teachers' ethnomathematical knowledge which are those indigenous activities that are peculiar within the learners' culture and could be introduced in the classroom for the teaching and learning of mathematics as the basis to successful implementation of those ethnomathematics concepts in the mathematics classroom. Such ethnomathematical knowledge are concepts such as: the cock-crows and shadow as a concept of time keeping, fingers-legs counting rhymes as a concept of counting numbers, tallies and notches as a concept of keeping values and records, market days counting as a concept of number base system. This knowledge, if acquired by the teacher could be used to facilitate the teaching and learning of mathematics.

Students, parents, educators, government and the populace are worried because of the persistent poor achievement of students in mathematics. Evidence shows that this condition is deplorably high to the extent that Nigeria student start competing for the last position instead of first in mathematics in school certificate examination among the eleven English-speaking West African Countries. Also, there is evidence to lend support to the fact that this poor achievement is as a result of non-utilization of appropriate teaching approaches in the subject. Because of the lack of appropriate teaching method in the teaching and learning of mathematics, students develop serious difficulty in understanding, comprehending, assimilating and remembering the concepts of mathematics taught to them in the classroom. They neither understood the basic computation, logic, fundamental principles nor the mathematic facts. This is because the examples that are presented to them by the mathematics teacher are abstract, alien Eurocentric and impracticable to them. They tend to believe on the primitive slogan that says that says; "mathematics make people to go mad". The effect of this mathemaphobia syndrome is what result in the persistent gross mass failure of students in mathematics in Nigeria at large.

This trend is worrisome to the researcher, because one wonders why all the method used so far are not capable of reversing this ugly trend. It is however noted that the use of ethnomathematics teaching approach (ETA) has not been widely tried out in Nigeria, particularly in number and numeration to see if it could reverse this poor achievement. Based on this notion,

the present study is interested in the question; would the use of ethnomathematics teaching approach improve students' achievement in the area of number and numeration in Akwa Ibom State?

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of ethnomathematics approach on achievement in number and numeration concept among junior secondary school students in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, it will help to;

1. Determine the difference in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State.
2. Determine the difference in the Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach in Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What difference exists in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State?
2. What is the difference in the Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach in Akwa Ibom State?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested for this study at the 0.05 level of significant:

1. There is no significant difference in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in the Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach in Akwa Ibom State.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest posttest non-equivalent control group was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all government Junior Secondary School class one (JSSI) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Akwa Ibom State with an enrolment of 64707 students from 229 secondary schools. 440 (214 Male and 226 Female) JSSI students constitutes the sample size from the target population. The sample size was arrived at by selecting 11 government secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State using purposive sampling on the basis of being a coeducational and government owned secondary school. The sample schools were explored using an intact class.

Mathematics Achievement Test on Number and Numeration (MATNN) and Lesson note on number and numeration topics prepared for experimental and control groups respectively was used as instrument for data collection. The students' achievement test consisted of twenty (20) multiple choice item questions, with four options constructed by the researcher to measure students achievement in number and numeration. The instrument was content validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation and two mathematics teachers. The reliability of the instruments was established through a trial test with 50 JSS 1 students who were drawn from schools in the area of the study but not part of the main sample. A reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained using Kuder Richardson KR-21.

The researcher had series of sessions with the teachers to educate them on the essence of the study and how to achieve an unbiased and better result. The achievement test which is the Mathematics Achievement Test in Number and Numeration (MATNN) was administered to the students as pretest and collected on the spot by the class teachers and handed over to the researcher. In each of the sampled schools, the JSS1 students were taught number and numeration by their Mathematics class teachers using the different instructional approaches under study. The Mathematics class teachers were instructed to adhere strictly to the note of a lesson prepared by the researcher, by using the same example for illustration. The answer scripts were collected back immediately by the teachers at the end of the posttest and were instantly handed over to the researcher. Mean, Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions and independent t-test statistics to test null hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ level of significance.

Results

Research question one

What difference exists in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing students' posttest achievement scores in mathematics on methods of teaching

Methods	N	X	SD
Ethnomathematics Approach	200	78.46	6.34
Lecture	240	57.00	6.20

As shown in table 2, the mean posttest score (78.46) of students exposed to the use of ethnomathematics approach in teaching the concept of number and numeration in mathematics is greater than those exposed to lecture teaching method with a mean score of (57.00). This shows that there is a difference in the mean achievement scores of the Mathematics student when taught number and numeration using ethnomathematics approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in favor of those taught using ethnomathematics approach.

Research question two

What is the difference in the Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation showing male and female students' posttest achievement scores in mathematics on ethnomathematics approach

Gender	N	X	SD
Male	96	72.36	9.59
Female	104	81.29	6.11

Table 3 shows that the posttest mean score of male students (73.36) is less than that of their female students counterpart (81.29) indicating a mean difference between the two sets of scores. This implies that ethnomathematics as an instructional approach, has more effect on the performance of female mathematics students than their male counterparts.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Analysis of independent t-test result on students' post-test achievement scores in number and numeration (MATNN), (N = 440)

Methods	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	Sign @ P<.05
Ethnomathematics Approach	200	78.46	6.34	438	35.77*	0.000
Conventional Method	240	57	6.20			

* Significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance; t-critical = 1.97, t-cal = 35.77, df = 438

As shown in Table 4, the achievement score of experimental group with mean of 78.46 is greater than that of the control group with mean of 57.00. The table also shows t-calculated value of 35.77 which is greater than the t-critical value of 1.97 at 0.05 level of significant. Thus, there is a significant difference in the Mean achievement scores of students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference in the Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Number and Numeration using Ethnomathematics Approach in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 5: Analysis of independent t-test result on male and female experimental group students' post-test scores in number and numeration (MATNN), (N = 200)

Gender	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	Sign @ P<.05
Male	96	72.36	9.59	198	7.78*	0.000
Female	104	81.29	6.11			

* Significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance; t-critical = 1.97; t-cal 7.78; df = 198.

As shown in table 5, the achievement score of female students with a mean of 81.29 is greater than that of male students with mean of 72.36. This implies that female students' benefited very well in using the ethnomathematics concepts in solving number and numeration problems as their achievement scores is greater than that of their male counterpart. The result in table 2 also shows that the t-test calculated values of 7.78 is greater than the critical value of 1.97 at 0.05 level of significant.

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This also implies that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students' taught number and numeration using ethnomathematics approach in favor of the female students.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one sought to determine the difference in the Mean achievement scores of students taught number and numeration using ethnomathematics Approach and those expose to lecture teaching method in Akwa Ibom State. The result showed that students taught using ethnomathematics approach performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using the conventional method. This could be attributed to the facts that students in ethnomathematics classroom explore examples of mathematical concepts and ideas that are rooted in the common plays, games and activities that take place in their various homes in solving mathematical problems in schools. The practical knowledge and relationship in which they have between the mathematics taught in schools and that which they practice at home through games, rhymes, puzzles, exercise, etc aid them in solving mathematical problems at ease more than other students who only depend on the conventional formulae and system taught in school. The finding of this study is agreement with Kurumeh (2004), whose result showed that ethnomathematics approach was more effective in enhancing and facilitating students' achievement and retention in geometry and mensuration than the conventional approach. Also in support to the findings of this study, Ado and Abasi (2014) found out that students taught using practical approach performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using the conventional method. This could be attributed to the students' practical work which provided them with ease in imagination and abstraction of mathematical concept. It enables them to think out the mathematical ideas which are contained within the various activities.

The second hypothesis was to ascertain the difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught number and numeration using ethnomathematics approach. The results indicated that female students taught number and numeration using ethnomathematics approach achieved higher than their male counterpart. This result therefore informs us that female students benefited more from this approach than the male students. Reasons for this greater improvement of girls through ethnomathematics approach may be as result that since ethnomathematics concepts is mostly centered on common activities and practices of the people in the community, it is relatively true that girls mostly dominates in participating in these activities than the boys. Mathematical games which are commonly played in the community such as: Counting rhymes game, the throw and catch game, stick (tallies) counting games, monkey-ground counting games. are mostly played by girls and participated by few boys. The dominated participation of girls in several of these games which form parts of ethnomathematics concept used for teaching in school may have resulted in the female high achievement score in the area of teaching and learning number and numeration. The finding of this study appears to support the views of Ndubisi and Ekwueme (2018) who found that male students were superior to their male gender counterparts in different topics in the studies.

Conclusion

The findings of this study serve as the basis for making the following conclusions; that ethnomathematics approach affected students' academic achievement more positively than the conventional method used in teaching their counterparts in number and numeration. It enhanced and facilitated higher and better achievement in number and numeration. Hence, ethnomathematics approach is not gender friendly

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Ethnomathematics approach should be adopted in our school system. If Mathematics is to gain popularity, capture the interest of the learners and challenges their intellect, the content must be made more appealing in terms of basic institutional approaches. This can be done by linking classroom instructions to the learner's immediate environmental experiences.
2. Mathematics teachers should recognize and realize the special role of ethnomathematics in aiding students to understand mathematics. That is, they should be sensitized through seminars, workshops and symposium on the usefulness and importance of ethnomathematics concepts.

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